

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MARK****FIRST NAME: TOSCANINI****PROGRAM CODE: ACA-401D****COURSE CODE: DIDOL****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSES ONE-FIVE

1. What are the critical steps involved in starting an academic essay?

- Procrastination and rushing
- Defining the question and analyzing the task¹**
- Limiting the scope and literature review
- Skipping the drafting phase

2. How should the body paragraphs of an essay be structured?

- Each paragraph should contain a single sentence
- No specific structure is required

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7.

- One paragraph for each reference used
 - Each paragraph should focus on one main point with supporting evidence²**
3. What is a recommended approach for effective essay writing?
- Procrastinate and write everything in one sitting
 - Write the introduction first, then the body, and finally the conclusion
 - Skip the editing and proofreading stages
 - Start early, revise extensively, and follow a logical order³**
4. How do experienced researchers think about their research aims?
- They focus on gathering as much data as possible
 - They aim to answer a question that others in their field want to answer⁴**
 - They prioritize their curiosity over the interests of others
 - They focus on writing a paper that will be well-received by their peers
5. What distinguishes pure research from applied research?
- Pure research aims to answer more significant questions, while applied research focuses on specific issues
 - Pure research is conducted in academic settings, while applied research is done in real-world contexts

² Ibid., 11.

³ Ibid.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 20.

Pure research is more theoretical, while applied research focuses on practical problems⁵

There is no difference between pure research and applied research

6. In which situations should you always provide a citation?

When you quote exact words from a source

When you paraphrase ideas associated with a specific source

When you use any ideas, data, or methods from a source you consulted

All of the above⁶

7. Why should online sources be chosen carefully?

Online content is often anonymous and unreliable

Online content can be revised or disappear without notice

URLs can change and make it difficult to find the original source

All of the above⁷

8. What is the role of limitations in a qualitative study?

They define the boundaries and scope of the study⁸

They present alternative explanations for the findings

⁵ Ibid., 29.

⁶ Ibid., 140.

⁷ Ibid., 143.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 438.

- They analyze and interpret the research data
 - They provide actionable recommendations for policy and practice
9. How should inconsistent or unexpected findings be addressed in the findings chapter?
- They should be ignored or overlooked
 - They should be noted with discussion of possible alternative explanations**
 - They should be analyzed and interpreted in detail
 - They should be presented objectively, without speculation
10. How does the dissertation defense contribute to the scholarly community?
- The defense is a formality and has no significant impact on the scholarly community
 - The defense provides an opportunity to publicly discuss research and evaluate its acceptability as a scholarly piece⁹**
 - The defense marks the end of the research apprenticeship and signifies the completion of the doctoral degree
 - The defense is a symbolic rite of passage with no bearing on awarding the doctorate

⁹ Ibid., 748.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.

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Turabian, Kate L, Wayne C. Booth, Colomb Gregory G, Joseph M Williams, Joseph Bizup, and William T FitzGerald. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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